

INTRODUCTION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE GOTHIC GENRE IN UZBEK LITERATURE

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Annotation: In our country, the principle of learning new methods and approaches in world literature, creative assimilation and active use in research was formed. Also, in the Uzbek literature of the period of independence, there was a practice of combining the principles of artistic re-embodiment of the world developed in the West with Uzbek literary and aesthetic traditions.

Key words: devil, peep, fantasize, aesthetic, colloquial column, soulless technocracy, controversy, consciousness, imperceptible

It is known that the picture of science fiction dates back to the second half of the 20th century-an unparalleled period of development of socio-economic, scientific and technical progress in its social development. "At the end of the last century," writes Herbert Welles, "no one was brilliant at Magic, no one believed in it and its results. At such a time, an idea came to my mind. Instead of confronting the reader with a devil or a peep, spells, you can follow the path shown by science if you can fantasize a little. It was not a big discovery. I just replaced the old fetish with a new one.

At the level of opportunity, I brought it closer to the real theory". Vivid examples of science fiction in world literature can be found as far back as Jules Verne and Herbert Welles. Notable works include Tamazzo Campanella's "City of The Sun" in 1623, Francis Bacon's "new Atlanta" in 1627, and Jonathan Swift's "Gulliver's travels".

These works promote the achievements of Science and technology, ideas of social progress. However, Balinese as a branch of literature, as a new independent type of science fiction J.Verne and G.Welles progressed in every way in his work.

This, of course, had a great influence on the national literature of other peoples. Today, Uzbek fiction is being laid the foundation by such young creators as Mahmudov, Tohir Malik, Khojiakbor Shaykhov, Murad Khidir, Anvar Kasimov.

The first work written by G.Jakhongirov in the science fiction genre was published in the 3rd issue of – "Gulhan" magazine in 1969. 1974 writer Tohir Malik collected and published his fantasy stories under the title "Black Angel". In

Tashkent, 1977, a council of young Uzbek fantasy writers was formed under the magazine "Science and marriage".

Even during this period, Uzbek fantastic literature was at the stage of learning from World Literature. Therefore, it was still necessary for him to continue and develop his achievements, relying on the main ideas and aesthetic directions in World fantastic literature. Because literary critics at the time had observed and criticized Tohir Malik's "the Black Angel" as sounding too much like Alexander Belyaev's "man-amphibian", "Professor Deuel's head". This was like an ax war on the vein of the Uzbek fantastic literature that was just emerging. Just as universal literary themes of any art, it is natural for fantastic literature to have its own and proper universal eternal themes.

The story's protagonist, Belden, a Western alien scientist, gathers homeless children under as if humanistic views and transposes them to large people by passing a terrible experiment on them, taking some of the Centers in their brains. With his "scientific" experiments, on the one hand, he prolongs the life of money bearing people, and on the other, he enslaves the poor by turning them into a "production" weapon". According to Belden's philosophy, humanity is made up of those who are engaged in science, control the state, and living robots-who are subject to their will, mat. This work by Tohir Malik calls for the separation of Science from cold, soulless technocracy. The story "I am not me" by Sam Mahmudov is also devoted to the topic of the controversy of "physicists «and "lyricists".

Traditional fantastic colloquial column in the work. With the emergence of a new painting teacher, Khamavi, at the Academy of Arts, where Nem studied, the idea spreads that the riches of innumerable and colorful nature drive humanity away from useful labor. The result of many years of scientific research, Ham creates new human eyes. These eyes are aimed at looking at nature the same "cold" look standard. Nem finds himself unable to find a place in the well when he hears hat every student should replace his eyes with these "robotic" eyes, and does not know how he came to the Garden on the outskirts of the city. Suddenly, a storm rises, a thunderstorm raining, and NEM is struck by his fire spear... When he regained consciousness, he sees a young man next to him. It was his second Me. In the story, an imperceptible person is condemned. True, even if the best qualities of NEM remain on the other side of it, the work ends well. Nem returns to his original. The work glorifies a person with a sense of love, high feelings.

Literature used:

1. SHarafiddinov O. On the paths of spiritual maturation. Tashkent, 2001

2. O'zbekiston Milliy Ensiklopediyasi. Birinchi jild. Toshkent,2000 yil
3. Hojiakbar (2001). Ikki jahon ovorasi (2001).pdf 23. Ziyouz
4. (2020). Hojiakbar nasri. Retrieved 07.03.2021 from:
<https://n.ziyouz.com/>
5. books/uzbek_nasri/Hojiak

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